

Rapid hazard assessment of the extremely large landslide threatening the Rules Reservoir (Southern Spain)

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Abstract

When an active landslide is firstly identified in a critical infrastructure such as a reservoir, a comprehensive characterisation and monitoring survey has to be performed in the shortest period of time to analyse the possible hazard that it may imply to the reservoir and surroundings. This paper presents the case of the El Arrecife Landslide, located in a slope of the Rules Reservoir (Southern Spain), as an example of geological and motion data integration to elaborate a quick and preliminary hazard assessment. For this purpose, we carried out a field survey to define its kinematics: translational in favour of a specific foliation set while rotational in the landslide foot. We also proposed a possible failure surface as well as estimating a landslide volume of 14.7 million m³. Concurrently, we applied a remote sensing and geophysical multi-technique approach to obtain historical displacement rates of the landslide up to the past decades. All the techniques could provide us results in a quick way. We made use of already registered satellite and aerial images through Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (InSAR) and Structure-from-Motion (SfM), respectively. Moreover, we carried out a Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) survey along a damaged road that crosses the landslide to obtain information of the asphalt layers and thus, inferring the vertical subsidence related to the landslide' activity. All of this collected information will be valuable to optimise the planning of future monitoring surveys (i.e. Differential Global Positioning Systems, inclinometers, ground drilling and InSAR) that should be applied to avoid further damages on the reservoir and related infrastructures.

Key words

Landslide, Reservoir, Quick hazard assessment, Geological data, Multi-technique monitoring, InSAR, SfM, GPR

1. Introduction

The study of a specific landslide must start with a geological and geomorphological characterisation to define its main attributes such as dimensions, structure, geometry or volume (Cruden and Varnes 1996). This knowledge is an essential starting point for not only planning and optimising monitoring surveys but also to provide a conceptual model for modelling the slope. Monitoring surveys are a key component of most landslide hazard assessments, that typically involves obtaining surface displacement rates measured over time (Clague and Stead 2012). Additionally, the temporal displacement patterns can be analysed to detect critical accelerations that may precede a catastrophic failure of the slope (Carlà et al. 2019). Characterising and monitoring a landslide is even more important when it takes place in a reservoir, where landslides usually lead to risky situations that may result in human, material and/or economic losses (e.g. Kiersch 1964; Schuster 1979; Spanilá et al. 2002; Wang et al. 2004; Gutiérrez et al. 2010; Reyes-Carmona et al. 2020a). For being such a critical infrastructure, the monitoring techniques must provide quick results by using already registered information for then, rapidly evaluating the possible landslide impacts on the reservoir. These requirements are also important to consider in case of an alarm situation.

Currently, there are a wide range of techniques that provide ground surface displacement data related to landslide activity: i) remote sensing techniques, that include Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (InSAR) (e.g. Massonet and Feigl 1998), Global Positioning Systems (GPS) (e.g. Brunner and Gassner 2003), Terrestrial Laser Scanner (TLS) (e.g. Teza et al. 2007) and photogrammetry using aerial photographs from planes (e.g. Kraus, 1997) or Remotely Piloted Aircraft Systems (RPAS) (e.g. Niethammer et al. 2012); ii) geophysical techniques, such as Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) (e.g. Lissak et al. 2015) or iii) conventional geotechnical monitoring systems like inclinometers or extensometers (e.g. Corominas et al. 2000).

Just some of these techniques can be applied to retrospectively quantify a landslide displacement rate by using already registered information: (1) InSAR applied to archived radar satellite images and (2) photogrammetry of historic aerial photographs. Moreover, the mentioned techniques can be used very quickly to obtain preliminary data that may guide the subsequent studies or monitoring surveys over a landslide. Regarding InSAR methods as the Geohazards Exploitation Platform (GEP) of the European Space Agency (ESA) can provide Earth surface velocity maps in just 24-48 hours (e.g. Manunta et al. 2016; Galve et al. 2017; Tapete and Cigna 2017; Foumelis et al. 2019; Reyes-Carmona et al. 2020b). On the other hand, Structure-from-Motion (SfM) techniques (Ullman 1979; Hartley and Zisserman 2003; Szeliski 2010; Fisher et al. 2013) allow generating landscape 3D models to identify the evolution of landforms with historical aerial photographs in a short period of time by comparing at least two different Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) at different dates (Snavely et al. 2008; Westoby et al. 2012; Eltner et al. 2016; Riquelme et al. 2019). In case of a landslide, the quantified changes can be attributed to its activity, being possible to estimate the displacement rate during a certain period of time.

Additionally, if a road crosses an active landslide, this infrastructure can also register old displacements just in case of having been resurfaced for maintaining its profile. In such case, one day Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) survey can be carried out to obtain profiles along the road for then, identifying the asphalt layers succession. In this way, it is possible to infer the vertical displacement rate along a road from the evolution in time of the asphalt layering (e.g., Lissak et al. 2015).

In this paper, we integrate the abovementioned methods in the study of the El Arrecife Landslide (Fig. 1), a landslide recently recognised by DInSAR techniques (Reyes-Carmona et al. 2020a). This landslide affects the western slope of the Rules Reservoir (Southern Spain), that leads to a potential hazardous situation. For this reason, we decided to perform an in-deep

characterisation and a multi-technique investigation of the landslide in order to evaluate its potential threat to the reservoir in the shortest possible time. We firstly made a detailed geological study to define the structure and conditioning factors of the landslide as well as estimating the failure surface and its volume. Following, we applied InSAR, GPR and SfM methods to obtain historical displacement rates of the landslide. Thus, our geological assessment can serve to design future investigations such as inclinometer and Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS) monitoring, topographic surveys or exploration drilling in an optimum manner. In the same way, the remote sensing (i.e., InSAR and SfM) and geophysical (i.e., GPR) techniques provided displacement rates of the landslide before starting any ground monitoring action, not only in a quick and efficient approach but also by using free-available or fast acquired data. This information also can be used to define future monitoring works with more precision. Finally, we integrated all the produced data to perform a preliminary hazard evaluation of the El Arrecife Landslide within the Rules Reservoir context.

2. Case study

The El Arrecife Landslide is an active translational landslide located within the western slope of the Rules Reservoir, in the Granada province (Southern Spain) (Fig.1). The El Arrecife Landslide is settled within the Permo-Triassic phyllites of the metamorphic Alpujárride Complex (Aldaya et al. 1979). The Alpujárride rocks enjoy several deformational events that determine their geological complexity due to existence of multiple structures (i.e., foliations, lineations, folds and faults) at both small and large scale and different ages (e.g. Jabaloy et al. 1993; Simancas and Campos 1993; Azañón and Goffé 1997; Martínez-Martínez et al. 2002, 2004; Simancas 2018).

The Rules Reservoir area has been affected by several slope movements during the last decades, being the subject of several landslide inventories (Fernández et al. 1997; Chacón et al. 2007). The most recent landslide inventory of the area was carried out by Reyes-Carmona et al. 2020a where the El Arrecife Landslide is mapped for the first time. The most noteworthy characteristic of the El Arrecife Landslide is that it does not show a prominent head scarp or any other well-marked landslide morphology, what makes it not easily identifiable in the landscape (Reyes-Carmona et al. 2020a). These authors presented ground surface displacement data of the Rules Reservoir area, obtained by means of Differential Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (DInSAR) techniques, which revealed the actual area of the sliding body (around 0.5 km²). Moreover, they estimated a mean surface velocity up to -25 mm/year and an accumulated displacement of 10 cm in 3.5 years for the entire landslide body.

The activity of the El Arrecife Landslide has been also evidenced by the N-323 National Road, that runs across the landslide. This road has constantly needed for repairing works due to the existence of bumps, cracks and partial collapses of the road pavement (Fernández-Motril 2013). In 2013, the Spanish Ministry of Public Works and Transport invested a total of 3.8 million Euros to repair 8 km of the N-323 National Road, what entailed the resurfacing of the pavement and the structural restoration of the northern abutment of the El Arrecife Viaduct (Fernández-Motril 2013), located in the southern limit of the El Arrecife Landslide.

In addition, Reyes-Carmona et al. (2020a) pointed out the potential hazard of the landslide, considering a rapid acceleration and a catastrophic slope failure due to its translational character. According to the authors, the collapse of a slide mass into the reservoir would have devastating consequences not only for nearby populations, in case of a downstream flash flood, but also for some infrastructures like the N-323 National Road and some powerlines.

Fig.1 a Location of the El Arrecife Landslide in the Rules Reservoir, Southern Spain. The main roads (A-44, N-323, A-346 and A-4133), some critical infrastructures (Rules Viaduct and Rules Dam) and other relevant landslides in the reservoir surroundings. b Panoramic view of the El Arrecife Landslide.

3. Methodology

Firstly, we performed a detailed geological survey of the El Arrecife Landslide, based on field observations. This step was essential to later estimate some important characteristics of the landslide such as the surface of rupture and its volume. Following, we calculated the recent displacement rate of the El Arrecife Landslide by a multi-technique approach. The used techniques exploit already registered information and they provided quick results of variable precisions (mm/year to dm/year) at different time scales (5-20 years). This was a key information to evaluate the landslide activity during the last decades.

3.1. Geological characterisation of the landslide and volume estimation

The geological characterisation of the landslide was carried out through a structural study and a kinematic analysis of the slope that led to the estimation of its volume.

Structural study

We carried out a detailed field survey that include a structural analysis, within and out of the El Arrecife Landslide perimeter. The most penetrative and visible structures in the study area are: S_{2A} foliation, usually is the main foliation in the Permo-Triassic phyllites (Simancas 2018) and F_{3A} km-scale folds, widely distributed in the Alpujarride Complex, fold the main foliation (Estévez et al. 1985; Simancas and Campos 1993). Therefore, we also considered that both S_{2A} and F_{3A} are the geological structures that mainly influence on the slope stability conditions of the El Arrecife area.

Kinematic analysis

A kinematic analysis by means of stereographic projection methods easily examine the direction in which a rock slope is more probable to slide (Wyllie and Mah 2004). The first step is to identify the main sets of discontinuities of the rock slope. To do so, we collected field measurements of the main sets of discontinuities in 5 measurement stations (MS) and named as MS-0*n*, being *n* a number from 1 to 5 for refereeing to each of the stations. In this way, MS-02 and MS-03 are located within the El Arrecife Landslide perimeter while MS-01, MS-04 and MS-05 are settled out in surrounding area (Fig. 2). We focused our analysis in measuring S_{2A} foliation planes. Then, we evaluated the potential of these discontinuities to result in slope failures by using the software DIPS, following the Planar Failure Analysis procedure

(Rocscience 2004). This analysis consisted on plotting: i) the poles of the foliation planes, to arrange them in different sets and obtain a mean plane for each set; ii) the average gradients of the El Arrecife Landslide slope, including the daylight envelope for each value; and iii) two friction cones, using the values of 20° and 25° , that represents the minimum and maximum internal friction angle of the involved rocks (i.e., phyllites) within the landslide (Wyllie and Mah 2004). The area of rupture is defined outside of the friction cone when intersecting with the daylight envelope of the slope. Any poles, if plotted within the area of rupture, represent planes likely to planar sliding.

Fig.2 Location of the 5 measurement stations (MS) for the kinematic analysis of the El Arrecife Landslide area and 3 profiles, acquired from the GRP survey: Profile “Transversal” (Profile-T), Profile “West” (Profile-W) and Profile “East” (Profile-E). The different areas (Head scarp, Sector 1, Sector 2 and Sector 3) selected for the InSAR time series plots are also represented. This information is showed above a 2 m resolution hillshade model.

Moreover, we used the WEDGEFAIL tool from the SAGA (Automated Geoscientific Analyses) Geographic Information System (GIS) to determine the terrain elements where failure on geological discontinuities is kinematically possible through the frictional feasibility criteria (Günther et al. 2012 and references therein). We used a 5 m resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) to carry out four simulations of slope failure scenarios. For each simulation, we obtained a map that indicates areas of possible ‘failure’ or ‘no failure’.

Volume estimation

The procedure to estimate the volume of the El Arrecife landslide consisted on, firstly, generating a 2 m resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the landslide area before being anthropically modified by the reservoir construction. We carried it out by extracting the contours from a 1995 topographic map. Once we obtained this DEM, we traced 6 longitudinal profiles along a preferential direction of the landslide and we drew the possible surface of rupture within each profile, which is based on the kinematic analysis, the geometry of the slope and its main morphological features (i.e., main scarp and toe). In this case, the preferential direction to trace the profiles was the one parallel to the main dip direction of the foliation planes within the landslide perimeter. Afterwards, we estimated the contours corresponding to such failure surface to generate a DEM. By subtracting the landslide’s DEM from the surface of failure’s DEM, we obtained a raster-type map that represented the thickness of the landslide body. The volume estimation was obtained after multiplying the average thickness value of such map by the area of the landslide.

3.2. Calculation of displacement rates of the landslide

We applied three different techniques to obtain mean annual displacement rates of the El Arrecife Landslide during the last two decades: InSAR was useful to provide a short-term displacement rate of very slow movements (cm-mm/yr), up to 5 years, while GPR and SfM techniques were used to estimate medium-term displacement rates of great magnitude (GPR > cm/yr; Photogrammetry >dm/year), for the last 20 years. Moreover, InSAR supplied information about the temporal pattern of the recent landslide's displacement by means of Time Series (TS).

Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (InSAR)

We made use of the Parallel Small Baseline Subset (P-SBAS) processing service, available at the European Space Agency's Geohazards Exploitation Platform (GEP) to derive the InSAR data. Thus, we launched two different processing, one in ascending orbit and another in descending orbit. For the ascending orbit, we used 101 Sentinel-1B images, covering a period from 30 September 2016 to 13 March 2020 (3.5 years) with a temporal sampling of 12 days. For the descending orbit, we used 241 Sentinel-1A and Sentinel-1B images, covering a period from 22 December 2014 to 19 March 2020 (5 years) with a temporal sampling up to 6 days. For both processing, the coherence threshold was settled at 0.85 and the reference point was established in a small structure to the south of the Rules Reservoir (Lat 36.848, Long -3.497; WGS84 projection). The main outputs of each processing were a set of points with information of the annual mean velocity and the accumulated displacement at each image date. Both the velocity and accumulated displacement were calculated along the satellite Line of Sight (LoS) direction.

To represent the mean velocity maps in both orbits, we estimated the stability range (i.e., the threshold for discriminating stable and unstable velocity points) as two times the standard deviation of the velocity of all the measured points (Barra et al. 2017). Therefore, the stability range was settled between 6 to -6 mm/year for the ascending orbit processing while it was from 5 to -5 mm/year for the descending orbit processing. Pixel size of the obtained points was 90 m.

Moreover, we calculated the horizontal and vertical components of the mean velocity data. We followed the procedure described by Notti et al. 2014 and Béjar-Pizarro et al. 2017, that is applicable when both ascending and descending orbits data are available. Thus, assuming a small contribution of N-S horizontal motion (Notti et al. 2014), we calculated the E-W horizontal (V_{eastward}) and vertical (V_{vertical}) velocity components in a raster-type map with a resolution of 90 m.

Lastly, we plotted the Time Series (TS) of accumulated displacement of the unstable points from the ascending orbit processing to define the temporal behaviour of the landslide movement and its relation to the reservoir water level variations, for being the main triggering factor of slope movement in the Rules Reservoir area, according to Reyes-Carmona et al. (2020a). We assembled the unstable points in different groups depending their distribution within the landslide (Fig. 2): i) the head scarp; ii) the N-323 National Road; iii) Sector-1, that corresponds to a smaller-size landslide within the lower part of the El Arrecife Landslide; iv) Sector-2, the central lower part of the landslide and v) Sector-3, that corresponds to the slag heap area. Then, we plotted independent TS for each of the groups of points (median value). Reservoir water level measurements were freely obtained from the public Andalusian Automatic System of Hydrologic Information (S.A.I.H. HIDROSUR, www.redhidrosurmedioambiente.es).

Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR)

We used a RAMAC Ground Penetrating Radar system (Mala Geosciences) with a 400 MHz antenna to acquire three radar profiles (Fig. 2): two of them along the N-323 National Road (i.e., Profile "East" and Profile "West") and the other one across the road (Profile "Transversal"). The Profile "West" is 647.94 m long and runs the western side of the road while the Profile "East" is 820.96 m long and runs the eastern side of the road (Fig. 2). The reference point (0 m) of the profiles' length was established in the northern abutment of the El Arrecife Viaduct (Fig. 2). The Profile "Transversal" was acquired transversely to the road and has a length of 13.42 m (Fig. 2). The radar signal could penetrate at a depth of 2 m underground, providing a profile resolution of 10 cm. The data were recorded with a sampling interval of 5 cm and a total time window of 55 ns. By means of reflected wave methods (see Conyers 2013 for further descriptions), we

calculated a terrain velocity of 9.6 cm/ns. The raw data was processed by using the GSSI RADAN 7 software (GSSI 2012). The processing chain of the raw data consisted on six steps: i) adjust to time zero, in this case, settled at 3.9 ns; ii) elimination of the air-ground contact; iii) gain, to reduce the intensity on the signal; iv) migration, to eliminate diffractions' effects; v) deconvolution, to increase the vertical resolution as well as cleaning the signal; and vi) vertical filter, in this case between 250 and 750 MHz, to remove background noise.

As the El Arrecife Landslide activity has caused a considerable damage (i.e., cracks, potholes, sinking) along the N-323 National Road during the last years, multiple repairs of the road pavement have been carried out (State Road Demarcation 2020, personal communication) and thus, a succession of asphalt layers can be detected by the GPR. Such layers are well-evidenced by continuous and almost horizontal reflectors along the profiles. The temporal evolution of this layering can be used to infer the vertical displacement rate along the road (Lissak et al. 2015), that can be also extrapolated to the landslide's displacement rate. Thus, the displacement rate can be estimated by dividing the thickness of the whole succession of asphalt layers by the total period of time of the road paving.

Structure-from-Motion (Sfm)

We applied the methodology described by Riquelme et al. (2019) to detect ground movements in the Rules Reservoir from its construction (2004) to present time. For this aim, we compared two different surfaces from the years 2000 and 2014. The 2014's DEM was generated by using Airborne Laser Scanner (ALS) data, freely obtained from the PNOA project (<https://pnoa.ign.es/el-proyecto-pnoa-lidar>). The 2000's DEM was generated by exploiting aerial photos and using the SfM technique. To apply this technique, it was necessary to insert Ground Control Points (GCP) into the photos. For each photo, several distinctive features were identified in the 2014's DEM (ALS-DEM). The coordinates of those points were extracted to generate the 2000's DEM dense cloud to finally, compare it with the ALS-DEM.

4. Results

4.1. Geological structure of the El Arrecife Landslide

The Alpujárride Complex phyllites are the predominant lithology within the El Arrecife Landslide area, which boundary is indicated by a small-spaced dashed line (Fig. 3). Within the landslide perimeter, phyllites outcrops appear considerably fractured and partially covered by debris or soil and colluvium deposits (Fig. 4a). By contrast, outcrops are better-preserved out of the landslide perimeter and phyllites shows a noteworthy level of tectonisation (Fig. 4b). The most recognisable tectonic fabric of the Alpujárride phyllites is S_{2A} foliation with NE-SW/E-W trend dipping SE (Fig. 3). A minority NE-SW trend dipping NW is also present. Both foliation trends evidence the existence of m/cm-scale minor folds (Fig. 4b), plunging axes around 20° to 245° , approximately, (see stereographic projection in Fig. 3 and showing a NW vergence. These minor folds are associated to the existence of a major fold, interpreted as a F_{3A} fold. The cross section in Fig. 3 illustrates this foliation pattern, principally dipping SE while NW dipping trend forms the short limbs of F_{3A} minor folds. The surface of rupture of the El Arrecife Landslide was drawn according to the plane 21/120.

Fig. 3 Geological map and cross section of the El Arrecife Landslide area. Poles to S_{2A} foliation and F_{3A} minor fold axes are plotted in stereographic projection (lower hemisphere, equal area).

Fig. 4 Field images of the Alpujarride phyllites in the El Arrecife Landslide area. a Outcrop of the main foliation S_{2A} almost covered by colluvial deposits within the landslide perimeter. b Outcrop covered by red-coloured soil deposits located out of the landslide perimeter, where F_{3A} minor folds and S_{2A} can be observed.

Such assumption would imply an oblique (towards N120°E) movement of the landslide body with respect to the maximum direction of the slope (Fig. 5a). Despite the whole mass may be sliding downhill though a planar surface of rupture (i.e., translational landslide), the lower part of

the landslide is affected by smaller-size rotational movements, evidenced by several secondary scarps (Fig. 5a). These movements are progressively eroding the El Arrecife Landslide foot, clearly influenced by the reservoir water level fluctuations. Moreover, above the N-323 National Road, we identified active piping phenomena (Fig. 5b) and several opened cracks with vertical steps up to 0.5 m (Fig. 5c). These findings are clear signals of the El Arrecife Landslide's activity.

Fig.5 a Panoramic view of the El Arrecife Landslide. Rotational secondary scarps are indicated by a red-coloured dashed line. The translational direction of movement is also indicated with a black arrow. b Photograph of the piping phenomena within the El Arrecife Landslide perimeter. c Photograph of a crack with a superficial vertical step of 0.5 m and 1.5 m depth in the El Arrecife Landslide perimeter.

4.2. Kinematic analysis of the El Arrecife Landslide area

The kinematic analysis is shown in two different stereographic projections, within and out of the El Arrecife Landslide perimeter. For both cases, the area of rupture is defined by the intersection of the slope's daylight envelope with the 20° friction cone (Fig. 6). In a first approach, 3 foliation trends are clearly noticed: i) a NE-SW trend, corresponding to the measurement stations within the landslide (i.e., MS-02 and MS-03); ii) a E-W trend, corresponding to stations located out of the landslide and close to its northern limit (i.e., MS-01 and MS-04) and iii) a NW-SE trend, corresponding to MS-05, located out of the landslide perimeter and close to its southern limit (Fig. 2). Within the landslide, almost all of the poles can be assembled in one set (Set-1) and it is defined by the mean plane 34/140 (dip/dip direction). Just one of these poles is plotted within the area of rupture, that corresponds to the plane 21/120 (dip/dip direction), being the most likely to generate the planar failure along the El Arrecife slope. We named this pole and its related plane as 'critical pole' and 'critical plane',

respectively. Out of the landslide perimeter, poles distribution is clearly arranged in two groups of poles that we named as Set-2 and Set-3, defined by the mean plane of 30/188 and 28/306, respectively. None of these poles are plotted within or near the area of rupture.

Fig.6 Kinematic analysis of the EI Arrecife Landslide, within and out of the landslide perimeter. The main discontinuity sets of the area and their mean plane are represented.

The previous statements are also confirmed by the analysis done by means of SAGA-GIS (Fig. 7). The 'critical plane' of Set-1 defines an extensive area where failure is likely to occur, specially within the EI Arrecife Landslide area. This is not the case for Sets-1, Set-2 and Set-3, as almost any slope failure areas are estimated within the landslide perimeter. These results led us to confirm that planes with orientations close to 21/120 (dip/dip direction) are potential to generate slope failures in the area and thus, it is reasonable to assume such plane as the possible surface of rupture of the EI Arrecife Landslide.

Fig. 7 Areas where slope failure is kinematically possible through each of the main discontinuity sets of the EI Arrecife Landslide area.

4.3. Volume of the EI Arrecife Landslide

Assuming the 'critical plane' as the surface of rupture, we traced 6 longitudinal profiles across the landslide according to the 'critical plane' dip direction (N120°E). In the same way, the surface of rupture was established as a straight plane dipping 21° (dip of the 'critical plane') for each profile. The resultant map of the landslide body thickness of the EI Arrecife Landslide is shown in Figure Volume. The maximum thickness is 72.6 m, estimated in the lower southern part of the landslide. Thickness values near to 0 m clearly define the head scarp, especially along the northern edge of the landslide and in contrast to the southern limit. Knowing that the

mean thickness value of the landslide body is 31.1 m and the landslide area is 473107 m², we estimated a volume of 14.7 million m³. According to Fell's (1994) classification, it can be considered as an 'extremely large' landslide.

Fig. 8 Map of the El Arrecife Landslide thickness.

4.4. InSAR results

Velocity maps

Non-stable points were detected in both ascending and descending geometries within the El Arrecife Landslide perimeter, mostly in the lower part of the slope (Fig. 9). As velocity was estimated along the satellite Line of Sight (LoS) direction, negative values indicate that points move away from the satellite, while positive values refer to points moving towards the satellite. For the ascending processing, negative values indicate an eastward movement along the El Arrecife Landslide slope, in addition to subsidence in flat areas. On the contrary, for the descending processing, the eastward movement of the landslide is indicated by positive values. The points coverage is higher in the ascending processing, for which we obtained unstable points showing a displacement up to 31 mm/yr in the southern lower part of the landslide (Fig. 9). This area corresponds to a small-size landslide, mapped by Fernández et al. (1997) and Chacón et al. (2007), and its activity was confirmed by the InSAR data presented in Reyes-Carmona et al. (2020). Along the N-323 National Road, displacement rates range around 20 mm/yr while the highest rate was obtained in the slag heap area, showing values of 39 mm/yr. By contrast, the descending processing shows a worse quality of the points coverage but displacement of the lower part of the El Arrecife Landslide, including the N-323 National Road, can be confirmed (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9 Surface velocity maps in ascending and descending geometries of the El Arrecife Landslide area. Red arrows indicate satellite azimuth (Az) and black arrows indicate the Line of Sight (LoS) direction.

Fig. 10 shows the eastward and vertical components of the surface displacement data, obtained by the ascending and descending orbits P-SBAS processing. Eastward displacement reaches values of -4.5 cm/yr along the lower part of the landslide, what is consistent with a mass movement downhill the slope. Vertical displacement or subsidence is registered almost in the entire landslide area, except from the head scarp. Thus, the mean vertical velocity is around 1.5 cm/yr while the highest value (-2 cm/yr) is registered within the slag heap area.

Fig. 10 Surface displacement velocity in the eastward and vertical direction in the El Arrecife Landslide. The landslide boundary is marked by a black line.

Analysis of time series of accumulated displacement

Fig. 11 shows the Time Series (TS) of the 5 groups of points within the El Arrecife Landslide area together with the Rules Reservoir water level variations. The TSs of the head scarp and the N-323 National Road, as well as the mean TS of all the points within the landslide perimeter are plotted in Fig. 11a, while the TS of the Sector 1, 2 and 3 are plotted in Fig. 11b. Such distinction refers to the difference in the TSs displacement patterns: almost linear in the El Arrecife Landslide, its head scarp and the N-323 Road (Fig. 11a) in contrast to the steeped trend of the Sector 1, 2 and 3 TSs (Fig. 11b). The steeped trend of Sector 1, 2 and 3 is evidenced by two accelerations periods (i.e., change to a steeper slope of the line trend) that fits well with two periods of downdrop of the reservoir water level: i) during the second downdrop, from autumn 2017 to spring 2018, and ii) during the third downdrop, from summer 2019 to

autumn 2019 (Fig. 11b). These acceleration periods are not observable in the main scarp TS, that does not show a significant displacement, nor in the El Arrecife Landslide or the N-323 National Road TSs.

Fig.11 Time Series (TS) in Line of Sight (LoS) direction of accumulated displacement of the El Arrecife Landslide using (a) ascending data, obtained from Reyes-Carmona et al. (2020) PSIG processing and (b) ascending data, obtained from the P-SBAS processing. The referred sectors of each TS are indicated in Fig.2. Water level variations of the Rules Reservoir is also plotted as a blue-coloured line. Grey columns indicate four periods of dropdown of the reservoir water level, from March 2015 to March 2020.

4.5. Estimated medium-term displacement rates

SfM

The difference of both obtained DEMs (Fig. 12 a, b) within the Rules Reservoir area is shown in Fig. 12c. A zoom view of the slag heap area and its estimated elevation change is also

presented for a better appreciation (Fig. 12d, e, f). Negative values are indicated in red and correspond to subsiding areas, while green colours correspond to stable areas. In order to quantify the difference between DEMs taking into account the error of this technique, we produced a histogram that shows the distribution of the elevation changes, where two Gaussian distributions seem to be present (Fig. 12g). We fitted these two Gaussian distributions and the R-Squared value was 0.993, showing a good fit. The mean (μ) of the first distribution (Dist₁) is -4.27 m, that is approximately close to the technique error, according to Riquelme et al. (2019). However, the second distribution's centre (Dist₂) is located at -7.94m. These values correspond to those located within the slag heap area. Therefore, to estimate the actual height variation, the difference of both means corrected the technique error. As the difference in time between both models is 14 yr, we estimated an annual subsidence rate up to 28 cm/yr within the slag heap area.

It has not been registered other changes in the area with enough magnitude to be detected by this technique (>5 m). Therefore, we were not able to date the movements represented by several scarps observed within the foot of the El Arrecife Landslide. We only can say that, apart from the subsidence in the slag heap area, no rapid movement occurred during the analysed period (2000-2014).

Fig. 12 Results from the Structure-from-Motion (SmF) technique within the Rules Reservoir. a 3-Dimension Points Cloud (3DPC) obtained from SmF procedure by exploiting aerial photos from August 2000. b 3DPC obtained from the Airborne Laser Scanner (ALS) data from December 2014. c Vertical change in meters, calculated from the comparison of the 2000 and

2014 models. (d) Zoom view of the slag heap area, from the December 2014 3DPC. e Vertical change in meters of the slag heap area, shown over the 2014 3DPC. f Vertical change in meters of the slag heap area. g Histogram of the elevation changes distributions. Notice the two different gaussian distributions $Dist_1$ and $Dist_2$.

GPR

The GRP Profiles “East” and “West” are entirely included in Fig.1 (Supplementary Material) together with a plan drawing of the N-323 National Road damages, based on field observations. Fig. 13 show this plan drawing (Fig. 13d) and some field photographs of the main damages found along the road (Fig. 13a, b, f, g) as well as two extracts of the Profile “East” (from 0 to 115 m) (Fig. 13c) and the Profile “West” (from 390 to 515 m) (Fig. 13e). In both GRP profiles, we identified several asphalt layers that have been progressively superimposed since the construction of the N-323 road, in 1997, until the profiles acquisition date, in March 2020. The minimum thickness of the asphalt layers succession within the landslide body is around 0.7 m in both profiles while the maximum thickness is up to 1 m in the Profile “West” and up to 1.2 m in the Profile “East”. Such increase in thickness towards to east of the road is coherent with the El Arrecife Landslide’s downhill movement. The minimum thickness of the asphalt layering out of the landslide perimeter is also around 0.7 m (Fig.14a). Therefore, there is an extra asphalt thickness up to 0.3 m and 0.5 m in the Profile “West” and “East”, respectively, as a result of the additional resurfacing of the road across the landslide. Knowing that the last layer of asphalt was settled in 2019 and the total registered time in GPR profiles is 22 years, we could estimate a mean annual subsidence rate of the road from 1.4 cm/yr to 2.3 cm/yr.

Fig.13 a Photograph of the northern abutment of the El Arrecife Viaduct. Notice the broken corner marked with a red arrow. b Cracks on the N-323 National Road surface. c Extract of the GPR Profile “West” (length from 390 to 515 m). b Plan drawing of the N-323 National Road that shows the main damages along it. e Extract of the GPR Profiles “East” (length from 0 to 115 m). f Photograph of a crack with associated piping phenomena. g Bump on the N-323 National Road, marked with a red arrow.

We identified a large number of vertical cracks within both GPR profiles, that are evidenced by cuts along the profile reflectors’ continuity (Fig. 13c, e). Associated to some of these cracks, we identified several “air-filled voids” that are related to opened tensional cracks as a result of piping phenomena. The majority of these cracks do not affect the most superficial asphalt layers and just a few of them are visible on the N-323 National Road surface (Fig. 13a, b, f, g). Along the road, we mapped several cracks that delimited two sectors; i.e. Sector 1 and Sector 2, affected by smaller-scale rotational slides within the whole landslide body (Fig. 13d). Close to the Sector 1, some damages can be appreciated within the northern abutment of the El Arrecife Viaduct (Fig. 13a) as a result of the viaduct push into the abutment, what required of repair works in 2014 ([State Road Demarcation 2020, pers. comm.](#)). Folded bedding and asphalt layers can be appreciated within the Profile “East” (Fig. 13e), probably associated with the abutment deformation. Moreover, we found several NW/SE incipient cracks as the southern boundary of the Sector 1 (Fig. 13b). Within the Sector 2, we found a NE/SW crack with associated piping (Fig. 13f) as well as a prominent NE/SW prominent bump (Fig. 13g) that defines the northern boundary of this sector. All of these findings are indicators of the El Arrecife Landslide recent activity, at least during the last two decades. Moreover, we were able to infer the -possible-northern boundary of the El Arrecife Landslide at 625 m within the Profile “East” (Fig. 14a). Such limit clearly separates the slide mass, characterised by the absence of reflectors along the profile, from the in-situ bedrock that show a well-marked bedding from 625 to 730 m.

Additionally, the Profile “Transverse” (Fig. 14b) reveals other morphologies typically related to landslide activity. The asphalt layers define a cumulative wedge-out, that is the result of a progressive rotational movement ([Gutiérrez et al. 2010](#)) and subconsequent deformation of the road. This finding clearly indicates the rotational kinematics of the lower part of the El Arrecife Landslide.

Fig.14 a Extract of the GPR Profile “East” (length from 600 to 760 m). b GPR Profile “Transverse”. The location of the profile trace across the N-323 National Road is indicated in Figure 13.

5. Discussion

5.1. Conditioning factors of the El Arrecife Landslide

The understanding of the El Arrecife Landslide have come through the detailed analysis of the geological and structural setting given that the geomorphology of the slope does not offer clear signs of the landslide type and characteristics. We have determined the great importance of the geological conditions, such as lithology or geological structure, in the El Arrecife Landslide generation. The slope is made up of phyllites, the main conditioning factor for the landslides in the region as around a 40% of the areas where the Alpujárride Complex rocks outcrop are affected by landslides (El Hamdouni 2001; Chacón et al. 2003). Moreover, from the mechanical point of view, slopes formed by phyllites usually have a great potential to become unstable, for being a coarse-grained rock with a high mica content and a low friction angle (20-27°) (Roopnarine et al. 2013).

The El Arrecife Landslide is also clearly conditioned by the regional structure of the Alpujárride Complex. Due to the high tectonisation and deformation of the Alpujárride rocks (Simancas 2018 and references therein), changes on orientation of main foliation are expected. Such orientation variability leads to different kinematic scenarios that may be likely or not to sliding of a slope. For the El Arrecife Landslide case, a favourable planar failure scenario is defined within the landslide perimeter for the Set-1 ‘critical plane’ orientation, in contrast to other plane orientations (i.e., Set-2 and Set-3) out of the landslide perimeter.

5.2. Estimated displacement rates of the El Arrecife Landslide

The integration of multi-technique results has proved to be an effective procedure for a comprehensive view of slope movements’ geometry and kinematics, as evidenced by recent works: e.g. Janeras et al. 2016; Peduto et al. 2021; Cenni et al. 2021. For our case of study, the selected techniques provided us a valuable information of the El Arrecife Landslide displacement rate at very different time scales. While InSAR were used to obtain a short-term rate up to 5 years, SfM and GRP techniques allowed estimating a medium-term rate; 14 and 22 years, respectively. One of the main advantages of applying InSAR and SfM is that both techniques exploit free-available images and follow automatised procedures, what can facilitate results in a few days. Moreover, all of these techniques can be applied and interpreted by different teams 100% dedicated to this task in a matter of about two weeks. By using the provided information, we were able to perform a quick evaluation of the slope kinematics that covered up to some decades.

The multi-technique that we carried out within the El Arrecife Landslide allowed us to correlate all the obtained rates for then, complementing and maximising the information provided by each method. Along the N-323 National Road, the subsidence rate obtained by the P-SBAS InSAR service (1.5-2 mm/yr) can be almost correlated with the estimated rate from the GPR data (1.4-2.3 cm/yr). On the contrary, the subsidence rate up to 28 cm/yr, estimated from the SfM procedure, significantly differs from the InSAR and GPR rates. Such difference can be well-explained as the slag heap could have been rapidly slide during the first years after its construction, due to the initial typical compaction and overall shrinkage of the anthropical filling deposits (Barnes, 1995). Our InSAR results shows a mean velocity of 3.6 cm/yr in ascending orbit geometry in the slag heap area (Fig. 9) in contrast to a highest displacement rate, up to 5 cm/yr, presented by Reyes-Carmona et al. 2020. Such underestimation of the displacement may be related to the difference in the spatial resolution (i.e., pixel size) between both data: 14x4 m (Reyes-Carmona et al. 2020) versus the 90x90 m obtained by the GEP InSAR service.

5.3. Potential hazard of the El Arrecife Landslide

Once a landslide is identified in a reservoir context, it is essential to discuss about the possibility of a rapid landslide acceleration or reactivation and a subsequent collapse of the slide mass into

the reservoir. The most dangerous hazard refers to the generation of an impulse water wave (Gutiérrez et al. 2015). If the impulse wave overtops the reservoir dam, a massive flash flood could be generated downstream the reservoir, between other devastating consequences: human and material damages in nearby towns, roads or powerlines, between others. The acceleration of landslides is a complex topic under discussion within the scientific community, probably due to the large number of factors that determine the potential of acceleration: i) the volume of the landslide, ii) its velocity, iii) the shear strength of the failure surface or iv) the resistance opposed by the reservoir water (Pinyol et al. 2012); between others. Even when considering just one influence factor, there is no agreement. As an example, with respect to the dip of failure, Gutiérrez et al. (2015) suggested the existence of a natural threshold around 20° for the development of extremely rapid rockslides, capable of generating impulse water waves. By contrast, Glastonbury and Fell (2010) concluded that the inclination of the basal rupture surface could be as low as 5°. According to the volume of the landslide, it is also difficult to establish a well-proven link with a critical acceleration possibility: the 1000 million m³ Mayunmaca rockslide in Peru (Kojan and Hutchinson 1978) and the 15 million m³ Guinsaogon rockslide in Philippines (Evans et al. 2007) both reached the same velocity, around 35 m/s. Under these uncertainties, the El Arrecife Landslide, that present a surface of rupture dipping 21° and a volume of 14.7 million m³ could be considered as a potential landslide for a fast sliding.

Despite there are not indicators of a catastrophic failure of the El Arrecife Landslide at present time, this fact does not imply that a rapid acceleration cannot happen in the future (Pinyol et al. 2016). The abovementioned authors referenced several landslides with a relatively slow motion along pre-existing shearing surfaces previous to a sudden failure: the Grijalva landslide in Mexico (Alcántara-Ayala and Domínguez-Morales 2008), the Qianjiangping landslides, China (Wang et al. 2004; Dai et al., 2004), Val Pola landslide (Govi et al. 2002) and Sale mountain landslide (Zhang et al. 2002). The El Arrecife Landslide TS reveals a slow and constant movement of the slope with no indicators of a critical acceleration (Fig. 11) although according to Reyes-Carmona et al. (2020), an acceleration of the whole landslide body is possible due to its translational character. Despite of this, we consider that the smaller-scale rotational landslides, located at the foot of the El Arrecife Landslide, are more likely to generate damages at short-term. These rotational landslides have been disrupting the N-323 National Road at least during the past two decades, as evidenced by GPR findings and field evidences, resulting in a constant subsidence of the road and its deterioration. Moreover, the InSAR TSs revealed higher displacement rates within the El Arrecife Landslide's foot (i.e., Sectors 1,2 and 3) as well as a correlation between the acceleration of the movement with periods of decrease of the reservoir water level (Fig. 11). These findings evolve the importance of a proper management of the Rules Reservoir water level, especially during water discharge operations. Additionally, it must be borne in mind that this reservoir is in an active seismic region, with a Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) up to 0.2 g (IGN-UPM 2015) what means that earthquakes could reach intensity up to VIII, according to the European Macroseismic scale (IGN-UPM 2002). These accelerations in unstable slopes could provoke their failure, as evidenced by other worldwide examples of earthquake-triggered landslides: e.g. Rodríguez et al. 1999; Boomer et al. 2002; Khazai and Sitar, 2004; Gorum et al. 2011. For this reason, the catastrophic failure of the whole landslide or one of its sectors is a possible scenario that must be taken into consideration. Regarding the latter scenario, detecting rapid accelerations that may be pre-failure precursors of a landslide is still a challenging task for the research community. Some recent studies demonstrate that InSAR is a suitable displacement monitoring technique for the recognition of such accelerations (Solari et al. 2018; Dong et al. 2018). Moreover, in case of critical acceleration, it is possible to forecast the time of slope failure by using the Inverse Velocity Method (IVM), developed by Fukuzono 1985. The IVM has been effectively applied to several landslides (e.g. Segalini et al. 2019) and it has also provided satisfactory forecasting results when using InSAR data (Casagli et al. 2017; Carlà et al. 2017; Moretto et al. 2017; Intrieri et al. 2018 or Carlà et al. 2019). For the correct implementation of the IVM to identify possible accelerations, the monitoring activity should be constant in time and continues as long as possible (Valletta et al. 2020). In this sense, the Geohazards Exploitation Platform (GEP) offers the chance to obtain daily InSAR results and it could be a promising tool to continuously monitor

the El Arrecife Landslide's activity. However, we consider that other InSAR procedures should be also applied to confirm GEP applicability. We also recommend to apply in-situ measurement techniques, such as inclinometers or GPS, between others. These conventional methods provide relevant information not only for validate remote-obtained displacement data, but also for using it as an early warning system (Chae et al. 2017). As a paradigmatic example, the Las Torres del Irazú Landslide (Costa Rica) proved the application of GPS real-time monitoring to successfully forecast the time of failure (August 2020) in advance by using the IVM (Muller et al. 2021).

Lastly, we consider that an inclinometer survey should be carried out to confirm and precisely define the depth of the surface of rupture of the El Arrecife Landslide and also monitor its movement. This information is necessary for a more precise estimation of its volume, an essential determining factor to correctly assess the landslide-related hazard (e.g., modelling of an impulse wave in case of landslide collapse). Our study will help in decisions related to where and how deep to drill.

6. Conclusions

The geological and motion data that we present in this study emerge the relevance of the El Arrecife Landslide, a extremely large landslide located in a reservoir context. The compiled geological data allowed us to estimate a possible surface of failure dipping 21° and a landslide volume of 14.7 million m³, as well as to stablish the lithology and the geological structure as the main conditioning factors. Moreover, we defined the landslide kinematics as an overall translational movement oblique to the slope together with a rotational movement within the landslide foot. The translational character could imply a potential hazard of fast sliding and collapse of the whole landslide within the reservoir, what would have devastating consequences. Despite of this, the rotational movement within the landslide foot is more likely to generate damages at short-term, specially along the N-323 National Road.

The performed multi-technique monitoring revealed that the El Arrecife Landslide has been active at least since the last two decades: InSAR provided information up to the last 5 years while SfM and GPR registered information during 14 and 22 years, respectively. The vertical subsidence of the landslide obtained from InSAR techniques (1.5-2 cm/yr) and estimated from GPR information (1.4-2.3 cm/yr) can be almost correlated. SfM provided a higher subsidence rate of 28 cm/yr in a small sector of the landslide foot due to the existence of a slag heap. The main advantage of these techniques is that results can be provided in a quick and easy way by using already registered information, what is essential to evaluate the landslide hazard in case of alarm situation. Moreover, combining different methods is key to complement the information obtained by each technique, improving our confidence in the estimated values.

Finally, we recommend to apply other remote and in-situ techniques for a continuous monitoring of the El Arrecife Landslide. InSAR and GPS are suitable methods for real-time monitoring and also for predicting a possible time of failure in case of a rapid acceleration of the landslide. On the other hand, other in-situ methods should be carried out, such as inclinometers or drilling surveys, to confirm the depth of the failure surface and the landslide volume. These attributes are essential for further modelling of the slope, as well as for an accurate landslide hazard assessment. For such purpose, our geological study offers a preliminary characterisation of the landslide that may guide and optimise the planning of future surveys.

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